

Determination of Heat of Formation of Associated Systems by Calorimetry

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Flow calorimeter studies with three donors [lauryldimethylamine (LDA), cetyldimethylamine (CDA), tri-n-octylamine (TOA)] and two acceptors [n-propanol and n-butanol] in isoctane as solvent are presented. The data have been processed by two methods, one due to Drago *et al.* and other due to Gol'dstein *et al.* Although the thermometric titration method adopted in this work is a prerequisite for the latter methods, it is not so for the former. It was found that the titration data smoothed for ΔH calculation by Gol'dstein method give better results with Drago's method. Nearly equal results are obtained with both the methods which shows the absence of side-effects and equivalence of two methods at $p = q = 1$.

The calorimetric method for the determination of heat of formation of the complexes has certain advantages over other methods¹. Calorimetric measurements give directly ΔH and also K at the temperature of study without going through the indirect temperature study of the equilibrium constant K . Thus more reliable data on the thermodynamics of association are obtained from such measurements.

The association reaction when there is only one equilibrium can be written as

If the activity coefficients are assumed to be unity in solutions and molar concentrations are used, the equilibrium constant is

$$K_C = \frac{C_k}{C_A^p C_D^q} \quad (2)$$

where C_A , C_D and C_k are the equilibrium concentrations of A, D and the complex respectively. In terms of initial concentrations of A and D, equation (2) can be rewritten as

$$K_C = \frac{C_k}{(C_{D_0} - pC_k)^q (C_{D_0} - qC_k)^q} \quad (3)$$

where $C_{A_0} = C_A + pC_k$ and $C_{D_0} = C_D + qC_k$ (4)

The object of any method to determine equilibrium constant (K_c) is to find the concentration of complex (C_k). Any physicochemical property (X) which obeys additivity law can be used for this purpose, and can be expressed in terms of the sum of the contributions of all the components of the solution,

$$X = \sum K_{inst} Y_i C_i + x_s = \sum X_i C_i + x_s \quad (5)$$

where K_{inst} is the constant of the instrument, Y_i the intensity factor related to the physical parameter being measured and x_s the property of the solution. When only one complex is formed,

$$X = x_k C_k + x_A C_A + x_D C_D + x_s \quad (6)$$

ΔX , the difference between the experimental value x and

the X_0 , calculated by assuming that no complex formation takes place is given by

$$\Delta X = X - X_0 = X - (x_A C_{A_0} + x_D C_{D_0} + x_s) \quad (7)$$

This along with equation (4) gives

$$\frac{\Delta X}{\Delta x} = C_k \quad (8)$$

where

$$\Delta x = (x_k - p x_A - q x_D) \quad (9)$$

In any method, one solves equation (3) by graphical or other means and finally obtains equilibrium constant K and Δx . The beauty and advantage of calorimetric measurement lie in the fact that if we can take into account by some means all the heats that are not due to complex formation then Δx gives us direct information about ΔH , the enthalpy of complex formation.

$$\begin{aligned} x_A = x_D = x_s &= 0 \\ \Delta x = x_k &= \Delta H V \\ \Delta X = X &= x_k C_k = Q \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where ΔH is in kcal mol⁻¹ and Q in kcal and is liberated in the reaction only due to complex formation in volume V or

$$Q = \Delta H C_k V \quad (11)$$

For strong complexes titration method is generally more reliable. Here, the amount of heat produced is determined in a calorimeter filled with one of the components A at concentration C_{A_0} while the concentration of the second component is changed successively. The curve Q/V vs C_{D_0} or C_{D_0}/C_{A_0} can be represented by two intersecting straight lines with different slopes if the complex does not dissociate. From the coordinate of the intersecting point one can compute C_k , ΔH and K_c (Ref. 2). If the complex strongly dissociates in the solution the curve would be blurred and other methods such as graphical are to be used. When $p = q = 1$, i.e. when 1 : 1 complexes are formed, the method proposed by Drago *et al.*³ seems to be most suitable.

When $p = q = 1$, equation (3) becomes

$$K_C = \frac{Q/\Delta H V}{[C_{A_0} - Q/\Delta H V][C_{D_0} - Q/\Delta H V]} \quad (12)$$

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which may be rewritten is the form,

$$K_C^{-1} = \frac{Q}{\Delta HV} + \frac{C_{A_0} C_{D_0} \Delta HV}{Q} - (C_{A_0} + C_{D_0}) \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) may be solved graphically. For each experimentally measured Q , a straight-line is obtained when K_C^{-1} is plotted against arbitrary values of ΔH . Due to the presence of the first term, which is rather small, the relation-

TABLE 1—HEAT OF COMPLEX FORMATION $Q(\Delta H)$ cal dm⁻³ POLYNOMIAL REGRESSION CONSTANTS a, b AND c (EQN. 18) FOR THE SYSTEMS INVESTIGATED AT 25°

Component I	Component II	a cal mol ⁻¹	b cal dm ³ mol ⁻²	c cal dm ⁶ mol ⁻³
n-Propanol	Lauryl-dimethylanine (1)	157.99	-319.29	289.46
n-Propanol	Lauryl-dimethylamine (2)	212.04	-429.43	392.26
n-Propanol	Lauryl-dimethylamine (3)	416.19	-874.77	791.88
n-Propanol	Cetyl-dimethylamine	158.59	-333.03	317.60
n-Propanol	Tri-n-octylamine	142.18	-218.38	258.49
n-Butanol	Cetyl-dimethylamine	185.78	-439.40	427.63

ship is not strictly linear and a narrow range of ΔH is to be used. Ideally, all the lines should intersect at one point which represents the unique solution of equation (13) and gives us the correct K_C^{-1} and ΔH . In practice, however, the lines cross at points which define a series of triangles the total area of which is an indication of the precision of the experiments. It may be emphasised here that titration experiment (C_{A_0} or C_{D_0} is constant) is not an absolute requirement for Drago's method. But it will be shown later that if one adopts titration experiment along with Drago's graphical method, one should get better results.

If, on the other hand, a titration method is adopted a more general approach is possible. This is known as method with 'elimination of one of the unknowns' due to Gol'dshtein and Gur'yanova⁴. For example, K_C can be eliminated by taking the logarithm of equation (3) and differentiating the expression obtained. Considering that K_C is independent of concentrations, one can write

$$\left(\frac{\delta \ln K_C}{\delta C_{D_0}}\right)_{C_{A_0}} = 0 \quad (14)$$

K_C is eliminated and an equation with one unknown, Δx , is obtained,

$$\Delta x = \frac{\Delta X}{2C_{A_0}} \frac{a \pm [a^2 - 4bC_{A_0} \Delta X' (q \Delta X - C_{D_0} \Delta X')]^{1/2}}{q \Delta x - C_{D_0} \Delta X'} \quad (15)$$

For calorimetric measurements, If C_{A_0} is kept constant, equation (15) becomes

$$\Delta H = \frac{Q[a \pm \{a^2 - 4bC_{A_0} Q' (qQ - C_{D_0} Q')\}^{1/2}]}{2C_{A_0} (qQ - C_{D_0} Q')} \quad (16)$$

where,

$$a = [p(p-1)C_{D_0} + q(q-1)C_{A_0}] Q' + pqQ$$

$$b = pq(p+q-1)$$

$$Q' = \left(\frac{\delta Q}{\delta C_{D_0}}\right)_{C_{A_0}}$$

where Q is heat liberated per unit volume.

After ΔH is obtained from equation (16), K_C can be found out from equation (12). As we shall see, although this method is superior to that of Drago's in many respects, it is very sensitive to Q' . But it has one advantage that with it, it is possible to verify if the assumption of $p = q = 1$ is valid for the system investigated here. We propose to apply both the methods to our experimental results and compare.

Results and Discussion

In an earlier work⁵ the heats, $Q(\Delta H)$, due to complex formation only were measured and it was shown that it could be represented in terms of a polynomial of the type,

$$Y = ax + bx^2 + cx^3 \quad (17)$$

where $Y = Q(\Delta H)$ and $x = C_{D_0}$ was fitted to each set of data and a, b, c are reported in Table 1. Results of four systems and the fitted curves are given in Fig. 1.

It has been pointed out earlier that thermometric titration is not an absolute requirement for Drago's graphical method. So it can be applied immediately to the unproc-

Fig. 1. Q vs C_{D_0} polynomial regression curve for (O) cetyldimethylamine + n-butanol (curve 1), (●) cetyldimethylamine + n-propanol (curve 2), (Δ) lauryldimethylamine (1) + n-propanol (curve 3) and (□) tri-n-octylamine + n-propanol (curve 4).

TABLE 2—CALORIMETRIC RESULTS : ΔH AND K^{-1} FROM METHODS DUE TO GOL'DSSTEIN *et al.* AND DRAGO *et al.* FOR DIFFERENT SYSTEMS AT 25°

C_{D_0} mol dm ⁻³	C_{A_0} mol dm ⁻³	Method of Gol'dshtein <i>et al.</i>				Method of Drago <i>et al.</i>			
		ΔH from Eqn. 18 kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH_{av} kcal mol ⁻¹	K^{-1} from Eqns. 18 and 12	K_{av}^{-1}	Range of ΔH cal mol ⁻¹	K^{-1} for same range	ΔH_{av} kcal mol ⁻¹	K_{av}^{-1}
n-Propanol + Lauryldimethylamine (1) :									
0.3500	0.00887	6.41		0.341		5500 6500	0.244 0.351		
0.2997	0.00887	5.98		0.297		5500 6500	0.249 0.349		
0.1991	0.00887	6.13	6.28 ± 0.30	0.309	0.322 ± 0.02	5500 6500	0.257 0.340	6.06 ± 0.18	0.304 ± 0.02
0.1501	0.00887	6.51		0.339		5500 6500	0.263 0.338		
0.1000	0.00887	7.07							
n-Propanol + Lauryldimethylamine (2) :									
0.3517	0.01196	6.48		0.350		5500 6500	0.244 0.352		
0.3092	0.01196	6.04		0.304		5500 6500	0.249 0.350		
0.1927	0.01196	6.13	6.26 ± 0.22	0.309	0.324 ± 0.03	5500 6500	0.258 0.340	6.06 ± 0.23	0.304 ± 0.02
0.1551	0.01196	6.41		0.332		5500 6500	0.262 0.339		
0.1057	0.01196	6.92							
n-Propanol + Lauryldimethylamine (3) :									
0.3985	0.02241	6.75		0.373		5500 6500	0.231 0.344		
0.2901	0.02241	5.53		0.240		5500 6500	0.238 0.334		
0.2050	0.02241	5.76	6.20 ± 0.68	0.260	0.300 ± 0.07	5500 6500	0.239 0.320	5.97 ± 0.53	0.280 ± 0.04
0.1507	0.02241	6.20		0.294		5500 6500	0.243 0.316		
0.1003	0.02241	6.78							
n-Propanol + Cetyldimethylamine :									
0.3374	0.00832	6.83		0.347		6000 7000	0.265 0.365		
0.2725	0.00832	6.23		0.290		6000 7000	0.269 0.360		
0.2164	0.00832	6.26	6.48 ± 0.35	0.292	0.312 ± 0.03	6000 7000	0.271 0.353	6.35 ± 0.11	0.305 ± 0.01
0.1592	0.00832	6.61		0.320		6000 7000	0.275 0.348		
0.1069	0.00832	7.17							
n-Propanol + Tri-n-octylamine :									
0.3532	0.00973	5.82		0.396		5000 6000	0.291 0.419		
0.2650	0.00973	5.19		0.318		5000 6000	0.297 0.410		

Table-2 (contd)

0.2169	0.00973	5.23	5.41	0.323	0.345	5000	0.299	5.35	0.335
			± 0.41		± 0.05	6000	0.402	± 0.13	± 0.01
0.1745	0.00973	5.41		0.341		5000	0.301		
						6000	0.397		
0.0963	0.00973	6.03							
n-Butanol + Cetyldimethylamine :									
0.3496	0.00914	5.52		0.244		5000	0.188		
						6000	0.296		
0.2694	0.00914	5.03		0.194		5000	0.191		
						6000	0.283		
0.2079	0.00914	5.27	5.41	0.214	0.227	5000	0.192	5.27	0.216
			± 0.42		± 0.03	6000	0.273	± 0.26	± 0.02
0.1483	0.00914	5.83		0.256		5000	0.198		
						6000	0.268		
0.1014	0.00914	6.47							

Fig. 2. Drago plot for cetyldimethylamine + n-propanol system using unprocessed data.

essed data is shown in Fig. 2. It means that the requirement of accuracy to obtain a good Drago plot is rather severe and even with the sophisticated flow calorimeter it was not possible to achieve the required accuracy when measuring very small magnitude of heat produced in the actual experiment due to very dilute nature of the acceptor in isoctane solvent.

The method of 'elimination of one constant' due to Gol'dshtein and Gur'yanova^{4,6} was next tried to obtain ΔH directly, as all the experiments were calorimetric titrations. If we assume 1 : 1 complex, i.e. $p = q = 1$, equation (16) becomes

$$\Delta H = \frac{Q[Q \pm \{Q^2 - 4C_{A_0}Q'(Q - C_{D_0}Q')\}^{1/2}]}{2C_{A_0}(Q - C_{D_0}Q')} \quad (18)$$

Equation (18) indicates that along with $Q(\Delta H)$ one requires to estimate the derivative $Q' = (\delta Q / \delta C_{D_0})C_{A_0}$. Originally the authors suggested graphical method for the estimation of Q' . But as the ΔH is very sensitive to Q' , we evaluated it analytically to avoid bias and errors. We used the constants a, b, c (Table 1)⁵ to obtain Q' at any desired C_{D_0} . ΔH obtained in this way was used to calculate K or K^{-1} from equation (12) or (13).

The results of all the systems studied at $25 \pm 0.005^\circ$ are given in Table 2. Except at lowest concentration, ΔH and K^{-1} obtained this way were found to be consistent with reasonably good accuracy. For every system more or less same ΔH was obtained at each experimental C_{D_0} . This supports the assumption of $p = q = 1$ for all the systems investigated. Otherwise each C_{D_0} would give different value of ΔH . In that event different values of p and q would have to be assumed until same ΔH was obtained at each C_{D_0} . While this is clearly an advantage, the main disadvantage of this method is that ΔH is very sensitive to Q' . This is particularly so at lower donor concentration where Q' changes very rapidly. This, coupled with the fact that lower donor concentrations heat evolved are smaller, affects the results at those concentrations. The systematically high value of ΔH obtained at lowest concentration of each system also indicates that equation (17) is not applicable to represent accurately the titration curves at lower concentrations. But as the experimental points were not many, it was not useful to try other forms. The lowest concentration was ignored in all the systems when the average heat of formation, ΔH_{av} , was calculated.

ΔH and K were determined at three acceptor concentrations for the system n-propanol + lauryldimethylamine. The results for all the three acceptor concentrations agreed reasonably well. It shows that the acceptor solution concentrations were correctly chosen and no untoward effects from the acceptor-acceptor interaction entered in the results.

Subsequently an intermediate concentration of 0.01 mol dm⁻³ was adhered to for the measurements.

Drago's method but with smoothed data was tried next and the results obtained were surprisingly much better. These were found to be not only as good as those obtained by the method due to Gol'dshtein and Gur'yanova but even better if the data due to the lowest donor concentration were ignored. The graphical solutions to equation (13) for a representative system studied is illustrated in Fig. 3. The usual procedure employed to solve K^{-1} here is to evaluate K^{-1} at all the crossing points and compute the average. However, this method leaves much to be desired. For example, if two measurements were made at approximately

Fig. 3. Drago plot for cetyldimethylamine + n-propanol system using processed data.

the same concentration the slopes of the plots of K^{-1} vs ΔH would be nearly identical. A small error in this case, would cause a large variation in K^{-1} . To eliminate these difficulties experimental condition was so chosen as to give K^{-1} vs ΔH lines which differ in slope as much as possible. The equilibrium constant was determined by computing ΔH_{av} and $\Sigma(\Delta H_{exp} - \Delta H_{av})^2$ at a series of K^{-1} values. The best value for K^{-1} was taken where $\Sigma(\Delta H_{exp} - \Delta H_{av})^2$ was smallest. This procedure would tend to ignore data points from closely parallel lines. These results are also reported in Table 2 where these are presented along with those obtained from equation (17). Close agreement between the results obtained by applying the two methods demonstrates not only the reliability of the experimental results but also the equivalence of both the methods at $p = q = 1$. But method due to Gol'dshtein Gur'yanova is more general and particularly useful when $p = q$.

Finally it may be pointed out here that using the latter method what one obtains is true values of ΔH . If the solu-

tions are not ideal due to the finite concentrations of the solutions and/or if solvents used have either electron-donor or electron-acceptor properties (e.g. benzene, dioxane etc.) which can form molecular compounds with one or the other of the components we normally get a apparent equilibrium constant instead of a true one. But as the equilibrium constants of the side-reactions, solvent concentrations and ratio of the activity coefficients for solution non-ideality correction are independent of the initial concentration C_{Do} the process $(\frac{\partial \ln K}{\partial C_{Do}})C_{Ao} = 0$ eliminates not

only the true equilibrium constants but also the correction factors. Thus ΔH obtained by this method are true values independent of any side-effects. Since ΔH determined by Drago's method are also nearly equal it means that the systems studied here are free from side-effects and justifies our choice of the solvent i.e. isooctane.

Experimental

In an earlier publication⁵ a method to measure heats of formation of associated systems by a Picker dynamic flow calorimeter was proposed. A Born-Haber type cycle was used to separate all the secondary contributions Q_n to the actual heat Q_{exp} produced during the experiment. The experiments was so designed that Picker flow calorimeter could be used with most advantage. $Q(\Delta H)$ the heat produced due to the formation of the complex only was reported there (Table 1, Ref. 5) for n-propanol + lauryldimethylamine at three acceptor concentrations, n-propanol + cetyldimethylamine, n-propanol + tri-n-octylamine and finally n-butanol + cetyldimethylamine.

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